

QUIZ

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PROGRAM CODE: DIPH

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **One of the following is not correct about paraphrasing of ideas or information produced by other author(s).**
 - The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author
 - You can just change a couple of words and rearrange the sentence structure¹**
 - The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used
 - The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 1* (Washington DC, Euclid University Press, 2015), 24.

2. **What are the reasons of citing a source?**

- To give credit to those who work for the source
- To assure readers about the accuracy of your facts
- To help readers follow or extend your research
- All of the above²**

3. **One of the following is a measure of trustworthiness that refers whether the researcher accurately represented what the participant thinks, feel, and do.**

- Credibility³**
- Dependability
- Reliability
- Transferability

4. **What is the advantage of using the WHO style guide?**

- It increases consistency
- It increases the level of uniformity
- It increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process
- All of the above⁴**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. rev. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

³ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (SAGE Publications, 2008), 77.

⁴ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2014), 1.

5. **What are the core elements of a research argument?**
- Claim, hypothesis, and reason
 - Reason, evidence, and storyboard
 - Claim, reason, and evidence**⁵
 - Claim, hypothesis, and storyboard
6. **According to the WHO style guide one of the following is correct way of referring to people without causing offence.**
- The disabled
 - People with physical disability**⁶
 - The handicapped
 - The blind

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 37.

⁶ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 58.

7. **What information of a cited source do you need to record to identify it in the notes or bibliography?**

- Author(s) or organization(s) who wrote or assembled the source
- Data that identify the source
- Place of publication, publishers name and date of publication
- All of the above**⁷

8. **One of the following is not correct about long quotations.**

- Long quotations will take quotation marks**⁸
- Long quotations are quotes that are over four lines
- Long quotations will be indented
- Long quotations look like a separate little paragraph

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 26.

⁸ EUCLID, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 1*, 20.

9. **One of the following is not correct about notes-bibliography style of citation**

- The name of the author is given in standard order in notes
- The name of the author is given in inverted order in notes⁹**
- Author, title and publication facts are given both for notes and bibliography
- Place superscript at the end of a sentence in which it is quoted

10. **A qualitative approach traditions or genre, where the researcher studies the cultural or social group in its natural setting by immersing in the day-to-day lives of the participants is**

- Case study
- Phenomenology
- Ethnography¹⁰**
- Grounded theory

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 92.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 11.

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World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2014.

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